

PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL ANTIDANDRUFF SHAMPOO

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ABSTRACT

The present study is based on the preparation & evaluation of poly herbal antidandruff shampoo. All the foam producing herbal ingredients was oversoaked over a night and the remaining herbal ingredients were heated to make a antidandruff shampoo & evaluation was performed by performing all the evaluation parameters hence we came to an conclusion that the natural herbal ingredients are more effective safe to use while comparing with the synthetic sources this herbal ingredients are having less expensive & more safe than synthetic sources. Further investigation have to be done.

KEYWORDS: Poly herbal anti dandruff shampoo, herbal ingredients, synthetic sources.

INTRODUCTION

Shampoos are most widely used cosmetic products for cleansing hair & scalp in our daily life. A shampoo is basically a solution of detergent containing suitable additive for another benefits such as hair conditioning enhancement, lubrications, medications. Now adays many synthetic herbal medicated and non medicated shampoos are available in the market, but the popularity of herbal shampoos among consumer is on raise because of their natural origin ,safe to use free from side effects. The present attempt is based on the herbal raw materials without using synthetic materials

INTRODUCTION TO HERBAL MATERIALS USED IN ANTIDANDRUFF SHAMPOO

S.no	Name of the Compound	Scientific name	Pictures	Genus	uses
01	Fenugreek	Trigonella foenum graecum		Trigonella	Manage blood sugar levels, promotes breast milk production in lactating women, hormonal balance, hair care, itchiness.
02	Hibiscus flowers	Hibiscus rosa-sinensis		Hibiscus l.	Hair treatment, skin hydration inhibit, aging reduces, stress relief immunity booster, cancer cell growth.
03	Chamomile petals	Matricaria chamomilla		Matricaria	Relieves anxiety & stress, insomnia, aromatherapy, anti-inflammatory, hair care, anti-microbial and cosmetics.
04	Eucalyptus leaves	Eucalyptus globulus		Eucalyptus	Anti-microbial, anti-septic, sleep-aid, anti-septic and anti-inflammatory properties.
05	Orange peel	Citrus Sinesis		Citrus	Stress relief, skin care, anti-microbial and anti-fungal. Antiinflammatory, skin brightening, Relieves acne dark spots
06	Ginger powder	Zingiber officinale		Zingiber	Nausea relief, Digestive aid,

					Reduces pain & inflammation, Relieves cardiac diseases, Aromatherapy.
07	Bengal gram	Cicer arietinum		Cicer	Dietary fiber, weight management reduces blood sugar levels controls anxiety and stress.
08	Rose petals	Rosa sinensis		Rosa	Smoothness, menstrual cramps, promotes skin health, improves mood.
09	Amla	Phyllanthus embilica		Phyllanthus	Immunity booster, promote radiant skin, strengthen hair, aids digestion, improves heart health
10	Reetha	Sapindus mukorossi		Sapindus	Treating dandruff, Natural shampoo, Hair growth & strength, prevents greying.
11	Shikakai	Acacia concinna		Acacia	Natural hair cleanser, conditioner, traditional medicine, rich in vitamins A,C,D.
12	Flax seeds	Linum usitatissimum		Linum	Digestive health, promote heart health, improve digestion, reduces hairfall, Balance hormones, Reduces cancer

01. Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum*)**Scientific name:** *Trigonella foenum***Order:** Fabales**Genus:** *Trigonella***Family:** Fabaceae**Therapeutic uses**

- Manage blood sugar levels,
- A promotes breast milk production in lactating women,
- Harmonal balance,
- Promotes hair growth.
- Anti-inflammatory
- Moisturiser
- Antidandruff & anti Hair fall agent
- Anti-oxidant
- Immunity booster
- Anti diabetes

Hibiscus flowers

- **Scientific name:** *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*
- **Order:** Malvales
- **Genus:** Hibiscus
- **Family:** Malvaceae

Therapeutic uses

- Anti aging effects,
- skin hydration,
- Anti Acne
- Hair treatment,
- stress relief,
- Immunity booster,
- Antifungal
- Antibacterial

Chamomile

- **Scientificname:** *Chamomile nobile*
- **Order:** Asterales
- **Genus:** Matricaria
- **Family:** Asteraceae

Therapeutic Uses

- Relieves anxiety,
- Anti inflammatory.
- Stress reliever,
- Antioxidant.

- Insomnia,
- Aromatherapy
- Hair care
- Anti-microbial.
- Immunity booster

Eucalyptus

- **Scientific name:** *Eucalyptus globulus*
- **Order:** Myrtales
- **Genus:** Eucalyptus
- **Family:** Myrtaceace

Therapeutic uses

- AntiAcne,
- Antimicrobial Agent,
- Carminative agent,
- Digestive Agent,
- Immunity Booster,
- Antioxidant

AMLA

- Scientific name: *Emblica Officinalis*
- Genus: Emblica
- Species: E.Officinalis
- Kingdom: Plantae
- Order: Malpighiales

- Family: *Euphorbiaceae*

Therapeutic uses

- Vitamin C,
- Immunity booster
- Antioxidant,
- Skin infections,
- Protective agent,
- Hair strengthener,
- Moisturizing agent,
- Anti acne
- Anti hair fall

Orange peel

- **Scientific Name:** *Citrus Aurantium dulcis*
- **Order:** Sapindales
- **Genus:** Citrus
- **Family:** Rutaceae

Therapeutic uses

- Skin care,
- To treat High blood pressure,
- Anti-microbial and anti-fungal.
- Antiinflammatory
- skin brightening
- Relieves acne dark spots.

Ginger

- **Scientific name:** *Zingiber officinale*
- **Order:** zingiberales
- **Genus:** Zingiber
- **Family:** Zingiberaceae

Therapeutic uses

- To treat diabetes.
- Used as anti inflammatory.
- To treat High blood pressure.
- Used to treat toothache.
- To treat dandruff & anti hair fall.
- Stomach pain & intestinal disorders.
- Analgesic & Anthelmentic.
- Relieves cardiac diseases
- Nausea relief
- Digestive aid
- Aromatherapy

Bengal gram

- **Scientific name:** *Cicer arietinum*
- **Order:** Fabales
- **Genus:** Cicer
- **Family:** Fabaaceae

Therapeutic uses

- To treat diabetes.
- Used as anti inflammatory.
- Controls anxiety and stress..
- Dietary fiber.
- To treat dandruff & anti hair fall.
- weight management.
- Reduces blood sugar levels.

Rose petals

- **Scientific name:** *Rosa sinensis*
- **Order:** Rosales
- **Genus:** Rosa
- **Family:** Rosaceae

Therapeutic uses

- Smoothness skin.
- Used as anti inflammatory.
- To treat High blood pressure.
- Used to treat menstrual cramps.
- To treat dandruff & anti hair fall.
- promotes skin health, improves mood.
- Blood purifier
- Aromatherapy.

Reetha

Scientific name: *Sapindus mukorosi*

Order: Sapindales

Genus: Sapindus

Family: Sapindaceae

Therapeutic uses

- Treating dandruff.
- Used as anti inflammatory.
- Used as Natural shampoo.
- Hair growth.
- To treat dandruff & anti hair fall.
- promotes skin health, improves mood.
- prevents greying.
- Aromatherapy.

Shikakai**Scientific name:** *Acacia concinna***Order:** Fabales**Genus:** Acacia**Family:** Fabaceae**Therapeutic uses**

- Natural hair cleanser.
- Used as anti inflammatory.
- Conditioner.
- Traditional medicine.
- To treat dandruff & anti hair fall.
- promotes skin health, improves mood.
- Natural foaming agen
- Rich in vitamins A,C,D

Flax seeds**Scientific name:** *Linum usitatissimum***Order:** Malpighiales**Genus:** Linum**Family:** Linaceae

Therapeutic uses

- Digestive health.
- promote heart health.
- To treat High blood pressure.
- Reduces cholesterol.
- To treat dandruff & anti hair fall.
- promotes skin health, improves mood.
- Balance hormones
- Reduces cancer.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The fresh proportions of various herbal ingredients like hibiscus flowers, chamomile petals, Ginger Powder, Eucalyptus leaves, Orange peel, Rose petals, Bengal gram, Reetha, shikakai, flax seeds, Amla, fenugreek are collected from the local market and medicinal garden of Dhanvanthari Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and authentication was done by Pushpalatha Madam, M.sc Botany at Singareni women's college, Kothagudem with an authentication number AVNRRDB-2026.

All the herbal parts of flower petals, leaves were air-dried properly inside the laboratory for one week. After the drying process was completed, they were ground to make up into fine powder. The fine powder was used to make further formulation & used in the preparation of making Poly Herbal anti-dandruff shampoo.

INGREDIENTS USED

Distilled water: Quantity Sufficient, Herbal ingredients like hibiscus flowers, chamomile petals, Ginger Powder, Eucalyptus leaves, Orange peel, Rose petals, Bengal gram, Reetha, shikakai, flax seeds, Amla, fenugreek.

EQUIPMENT USED

- Beakers
- Funnel
- Petri dishes
- Measuring cylinder
- Glass rod
- Conical flask
- Weighing balance
- Mixer grinder
- Heating mantle
- Dessicator
- Refrigerator
- Humidity chamber
- Thermometer
- Stalagmometer

PROCEDURE FOR PREPARATION OF POLY HERBAL ANTIDANDRUFF SHAMPOO

Poly herbal shampoos are prepared by soaking ingredients like Reetha 50gm, Shikakai 50gms, Fenugreek seeds 50gm, Dried Amla fruit 50gm, In an 1000ml of water after 24 hours of soaking filter the above mixture with the help of a muslin cloth. keep the filtrate a side.

Now take the dried herbal ingredients like hibiscus flowers(25gm), eucalyptus(25gm), orange peel(10gm), chamomile(10gm), rose petals(10gm), Bengal gram(10gm), ginger powder(10gm) was taken in a separate bowl & addition of 2000ml of distilled water, heat it under low flame while heating add flax seeds then heat it for 1 hour then cool the mixture after cooling filter the filtrate.

Now combine both the filtrates if required add parabean & sulphate free Shampoo base & tea tree oil perfumery to the above mixtures then packed in a suitable air tight containers store in a cool place and perform evaluation tests

Evaluation parameters: Organoleptic Evaluation: The study of colour, odour & appearance were studied for poly Herbal Antidan druff shampoo.

Physical Evaluation: Physical evaluation parameters like PH, Skin irritancy test ,Foam height checked.

PH: PH of the prepared poly Herbal Antidandruff shampoo were checked separately.

Skin Irritancy Test: For performing skin irritancy test 10 Healthy Volunteers were selected. The prepared Poly Herbal Antidandruff shampoo was applied on the palm of 5 healthy volunteers & time was noted, Irritancy, redness, Dryness and itching like parameters were checked.

Foam Test: 1ml of Poly Herbal Antidandruff shampoo was taken & dispersed in 25ml of Distilled water then transferred in 100ml measuring cylinder, volume was made upto 50ml with distilled water. Shake it for 30 times and place aside to stand as well as measured the foam height above the aqueous volume.

Foaming ability & Foaming stability: Cylinder method shape is used for determining the foaming ability. Put about 50ml 1% shampoo solution into a 250ml graduated cylinder cover the cylinder by hand & shake it for 10 times. Record the total volumes of the foam contains after 1mintue while shaking calculate only the foam volume immediately after shaking record the volume of foam 1,5,10,15,20,25,30 mintues.

Determination of percentage of solid: weigh a clean dry evaporate dish& add 4gm of shampoo to the evaporating dish weigh it shampoo along with dish. Now keep the dish on the hotplate until the liquid portion gets evaporated. Now the weight of sample only solids after drying is calculated.

Wash Ability: Apply the formulation on the skin is an extent of washing with water & check it manually.

Surface tension measurement: The surface tension of 10% W/v shampoo is determine by using stalagmometer chromic acid purified water. Calculate the surface tension by using the equation

$$R_2 = W_3 - W_1 \times N_1 \times R_1 / W_2 - W_1 \times N_2$$

Where W₁=weight of empty beaker

W₂=weight of beaker with distilled water

W₃=weight of beaker with shampoo solution

N1= No of drops of distilled water

N2=No of drops of shampoo solution

R1=Surface tension of distilled water at room temperature

R2=Surface tension of shampoo solution.

Stability studies: Study the thermal stability of formulation by placing in glass tube and then place in a humidity chamber at 45° and 75° relative humidity. Inspect the appearance & physical stability for a period of 3 months at an interval of 1month.

Results & Discussion: PolyHerbal Antidandruff Shampoo (2000ML).

S: No	Ingredients	Quantity
1	Fenu greek	25gm
2	Hibiscus	25gm
3	Rose petals	25gm
4	Chamomile petals	25gm
5	Eucalyptus Leaves	50gm
6	Orange peel	15gm
7	Shikakai	50gm
8	Reetha	50gm
9	Ginger	15gm
10	Bengal gram powder	50gm
11	Flax Seeds	50gm
12	Amla	30gm
13	Distilled water	QS

DISCUSSION (FORMULATION)

From the above polyherbal antidandruff shampoos, The formulations were prepared by using various herbal extracts like Fenu greek, Hibiscus, Rose petals, Chamomile petals, Bengal gram powder, Reetha, Shikakai, Amla, Ginger, Orange peel, Flax Seeds, Eucalyptus Leaves, by soaking foaming agents and consistency agents like reetha, shikakai, fenugreek, flax seeds, amla overnight while pouring 1000ml of water & Filter the filtrate considered as PART-1.

The remaining ingredients like Bengal gram, rose petals, hibiscus, Orange peel, eucalyptus leaves, ginger powder, chamomile was taken in a bowl heat it under low flame for about 1 hour & cool it for 2 hours & filter the filtrate considered as PART-2.

Now combine both the filtrates all tea tree oil as perfumery pack in a suitable container & Perform different Individual Evaluation Tests for testing Polyherbal Antidandruff shampoo.

Evaluation parameters for Poly herbal Antidandruff shampoo

Organoleptic Evaluation: The study of colour, odor & appearance were studied for alcoholic Herbal Hand sanitizers.

Colour	Odour	Appearance
Light brown	Aromatic	Ease

Physical Evaluation: Physical evaluation parameters like PH, Viscosity, Skin irritancy, Foam height checked.

PH	Viscosity	Skin irritancy	Foam test
6	Non viscous	Non irritant	Foam height increased

FOAM ABILITY & FOAM STABILITY

Quantity in MI	Time	Foaming quantity
1	5	1.5
5	10	5.5
10	15	15.8
15	20	20.6
20	25	25.7
25	30	30.8
30	35	35.9

Based upon the foam ability & foam stability for every 5 minutes of time interval there is an increase in the quantity of foam we can observe clearly in the table 1.5,5.5,15.8,20.6,25.7,30.8,35.9ml respectively

SURFACE TENSION	STABILITY STUDIES
25.16	Physically stable after 3 months

CONCLUSION

Herbal based shampoo base was prepared from various plant sources were selected & authentication was done from an botanist then the plants air dried, Grinded into fine powder then the above herbal ingredients was made into 2000ml Poly Herbal antidandruff shampoo. From the above discussion & performing various evaluation parameters hence we came to conclusion that Poly Herbal antidandruff shampoos are effective in destroying dandruff dirt & imparting healthy hair hence we recommend Poly Herbal antidandruff shampoos is more effective than that synthetic sources. further investigation have to be done.

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